

METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING INDEPENDENT THINKING IN 7-9 GRADES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Annotatsiya: Ingliz tili o'quv predmeti sifatida o'quvchilarning umumiy ta'limiga ta'sir qiladi, ularning tafakkuri va nutqini rivojlantiradi. Chet tilini o'rgatish orqali o'quvchilar berilgan til haqida dastlabki tushunchaga ega bo'ladilar, uni o'z ona tilidan ajratib turadigan xususiyatlardan xabardor bo'ladilar; bu esa o'quvchining dunyoqarashini kengaytirishga ham, ona tilini yaxshiroq tushunishga ham yordam beradi. Ingliz tilini o'rganish talabalarning o'rganilayotgan tilning geografiyasi, tarixi va adabiyoti haqidagi tushunchalarini yaxshilashga yordam beradi. Chet tillarini bilish xalqlarning o'tmishiga kirib borishga, ularning bugunini bilishga, kelajagini oldindan bilishga yordam beradi va jahon madaniyati durdonalarini qadrlashga yordam beradi. Bu milliy cheklovlar va torlikni bartaraf etishning samarali vositalaridan biri bo'lib, bu holat chet tilining o'rta va oliy ta'limning majburiy tarkibiy qismi ekanligini tushuntirishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: Fikrlash, nutq, mustaqil fikrlash, shaxsning nutqini rivojlantirish, tarjima tezligi uchun mashqlar

Abstract: English as an academic subject influences the general education of students, develops their thinking and speech. By teaching a foreign language, students gain an initial understanding of a given language, become aware of the features that distinguish it from their native language, which contributes to both broadening the student's horizons and a better understanding of their native language. Studying English helps improve students' understanding of geography, history, and literature of the country of the language being studied. Knowledge of foreign languages contributes to penetration into the past of peoples, knowledge of their present, anticipation of the future, and helps to appreciate the masterpieces of world culture. This is one of the effective means of overcoming national limitations and narrowness; this circumstance can explain the fact that a foreign language is a compulsory component of secondary and higher education.

Key words: Thought, speech, independent thinking, speech development of personality, exercises for translation speed

Introduction

The problem of the influence exerted by the prevailing type of thinking of students on the process of learning a foreign language is one of the least developed problems of modern educational psychology. In the modern world, there is a clear tendency to improve existing methods of teaching foreign languages, as well as to

search for new effective approaches that make it possible to make a qualitative leap in the teaching of this discipline. Computer technologies using words of non-Russian origin, ubiquitous the penetration into the Russian language of new foreign language terms from various spheres of public life dictates as an urgent need confident command of several languages. In this regard, at the present stage of social development, research devoted to the optimization of the process is of great importance. Teaching and studying psychological factors influencing students' learning knowledge of a foreign language. These factors undoubtedly include thinking.

Literature Review

Despite the fact that various aspects of thinking are the object of close attention of many specialists, a huge number of unresolved issues remain. In domestic and foreign psychological and pedagogical literature raises numerous problems associated with the search for generally valid foundations and criteria for understanding the specifics of thinking. Of particular relevance for the purposes of our article are works directly related to the problems of thinking and ways of its development. In this regard, it is worth highlighting the works of philosophers: N.S. Avtonomova, Aristotle, V.F. Asmusa, B.C. Bibler, G. Hegel, R. Descartes, E.V. Ilyenkova, I. Kant, B.M. - Kedrova, P.V. Kopnina, A.F. Loseva, A.N. Luka, M.K. Mamardashvili, T.I. Oizerman, M.M. Rosenthal, O.Ya. Sivkova and others; research by psychologists and teachers: V.P. Andronova, D.B. Bogoyavlenskaya, E. de Bono, J. Bruner, A.V. Brushlinsky, M. Wertheimer, L.S. Vygotsky, R.V. Gabdreeva, P.Ya. Galperina, J.Guilford, V.V. Davydova, V.N. Druzhinina, J. Dewey, A.Z. Zaka, V.P. Zinchenko, A.A.Leontyeva, A.N. Leontyeva, A.K. Markova, A.M. Matyushkina, J. Piaget, Y.A. Ponomarev, P. Richard, S.L. Rubinshteina, B.M. Teplova, O.K. Tikhomirov, E. Torrance and etc.[1]

Research Methodology

We have to admit that one of the most significant difficulties when considering the problems of thinking is, in our opinion, a large number of discrepancies associated with ambiguity and variability most of the terms used by psychologists and didactics. Researcher faces the need for a categorical definition of almost all concepts. This creates methodological and conceptual inconsistency, making it difficult development of linguodidactics and psychological sciences. [2]

Thinking is inextricably linked with a speech. Thought can neither arise, nor flow, nor exist outside of language, outside of speech. Thinking occurs in speech form People who are equally fluent several languages, clearly understand in which in

language they think at every given moment. In speech, thought is not only formulated, but also formed, developed. [3]

We have determined what is characteristic of the educational process in high school is also that knowledge, received in the field of one academic subject are given in connection with other knowledge, thus creating a system knowledge Therefore, to learn a foreign language (English) good knowledge of the native language is of great importance (Uzbek) language.

One who speaks his native language perfectly, capable of learning any foreign language. Language is means of communication between people Communicating with each other, people use words and use grammar rules of a particular language. Language and speech are inextricably connected, represent a unity that is expressed in that historically the language of any people was created and developed in the process of verbal communication between people. Teaching foreign languages promotes speech development and independent thinking. Systematically, taking into account the gradual development of speech activity entails is independent thinking.

When teaching English, we use specific methods of educational work. For each method characterized by its own special interaction between teacher and students, in during which the teacher organizes cognitive activities students aimed at mastering knowledge and skills. This interaction is related to the development and formation of the student's personality. Teaching theory and practice show that choice the method of educational work depends on several factors

- from the general purpose and content;
- on the didactic purpose of the lesson.

Depending on the content of the educational material, which should be the subject of our article, in lessons are used presentation of educational material, conversation, independent work (exercises, dictation, presentation, essay). [4]

The lesson largely depends on the age characteristics of students, their level of knowledge and skills. In addition, the teacher's training, his skill also may have a certain influence on the choice of teaching methods work. Every teacher needs to constantly improve their teaching skills and use in practice all methods appropriate requirements of life, use comprehensively, in interaction, implementing educational, experience and developing learning functions. [5]

Analysis and Results

When carrying out experimental work, we used the following types of tasks and exercises for experimental group:

1. game exercises that develop interest in learning language,

2. exercises aimed at developing creativity thinking,
 3. exercises aimed at developing independent thinking,
 4. exercises for speed of thinking, providing Simultaneous translation,
 5. exercises aimed at developing culture, love for Homeland
- and used traditional methods of teaching English for control group.

Students in experimental classes much higher than the level in control classes, which confirms the effectiveness of the methodology we have developed learning English on the basis of native language.

Experimental studies have shown that the advantage of the teaching methodology we have developed is that it takes into account the influence of the native language into the foreign language being studied (English) Based on comparative linguistic analysis of the structure of native and foreign languages, our methodology allows you to achieve optimization of foreign language teaching and takes into account difficulties for students in mastering a foreign language. Reveals the causes of typical errors, makes it possible to develop the most rational ways to overcome these errors, allows you to reduce the time and effort spent on foreign language teaching.

We have determined that mastering the system of another language follows the path of either transfer, or correction, or formation of new speech skills

Establishing the relationship between native and foreign (English) languages comparative analysis influences the choice of methodological techniques, since for students of different nationalities when studying the same material, various difficulties arise due to specific inconsistencies between the native and target languages.

Conclusion

Knowledge in a certain degree of native language has a significant impact on skills and abilities acquired by students. This influence is twofold character when transferred it can contribute to mastery of foreign language, and with interference it complicates and prevents it. This is explained by the fact that by the beginning of studying a foreign language, the student has already developed certain stereotypes of mastery of his native speech, which he spontaneously transfers to the foreign language being studied. The student understands foreign language based on skills and abilities developed by him on materials of his native language, which leads to the occurrence of a number of typical errors in foreign language speech.

Mastering the system of another language follows the path of either transfer, or correction, or formation of new speech skills. Establishing the relationship between

native (Uzbek) and foreign (English) languages comparative analysis influences the choice of methodological techniques, since for students of different nationalities when studying the same material, various difficulties arise due to specific inconsistencies between the native and target languages.

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